

Project Impact Report

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Authors:	Joakim Munkhammar, Uppsala University Claudia Luger-Bazinger & David Leistner, Salzburg Research Martin Loidl, University of Salzburg Svitlana Baliuk, Sustainability InnoCenter Sebastian Gatscha, TraffiCon

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Administrative Information

Basic information on the DyMoN project and the present deliverable:

Project title	Dynamic Mobility Nudge: Shaping sustainable urban mobility behaviour with real-time, user generated and public open data
Project coordinator	Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH (SRFG), Salzburg, Austria; project coordinator: Dr. Claudia Luger-Bazinger
Project partners	University of Salzburg, Department of Geoinformatics, Austria Trafficon – Traffic Consultants GmbH, Germany Uppsala University, Department of Civil and Industrial Engineering and Built Environment, Sweden Sustainability InnoCenter, Sweden
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Purpose of the document

This document describes the impact of the project, based on the achieved results and the dissemination of these results within the project. The document uses results from WP 2, 3, 4 and insights from WP 6. This document results of WP 5 (“Project evaluation and impact assessment”), T5.3 (“Assessment of project impact”), for estimating potential impact of project results and of nudging influencing mobility choices.

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the impact of the DyMoN project, categorized into scientific, societal and environment impact as well as economic impact. Each impact area is further separated into impact that could be achieved during the project duration as well as impact that goes beyond the project time. The DyMoN project has delivered work on development, implementation and simulation of digital, data-driven nudges in real life settings. Within this research project, the consortium has achieved not only scientific, but also societal environmental and economic impact that goes beyond the project duration. This project has delivered work on development, implementation and simulation of digital, data-driven nudges in real life settings. It has broadened the scientific field by providing new approaches to mobility behaviour change and the design of nudges and behavioural interventions in the mobility field, and has disseminated the results to cities, municipalities and local communities, supporting the modal shift towards more sustainable mobility in its environmental impact. It also opened the door to economic studies of nudging that could be tested in real life settings. In the long run, the project has impact on the design and evaluation of sustainable mobility nudges so that there can be potential wide-spread use of this in cities that is followed by a better quality of life within urban areas.

1 Introduction

Cities face the challenge of promoting sustainable mobility to reduce CO2 emissions, improve air quality, avoid pollutants and noise, and thereby make the city a more liveable place. A core objective is to enable and encourage the necessary shift from using fossil-fuel vehicles towards more sustainable mobility modes, i.e., walking, cycling, using public transport. To achieve this, cities can use “hard” measures such as congestion charges, car-free streets and removal of parking space or apply “soft” methods of nudging to steer citizens towards voluntarily changing their mobility behaviours.

The road to sustainable mobility is paved by changes in technology and behaviour. Nudges and other digital behavioural interventions for sustainable mobility are one potential cornerstone for this, but the challenges involve identifying which behavioural interventions to use, how to implement them and evaluating what impact they will have.

The high use of mobile devices (smartphones, tablets) and increasing familiarity of citizens with mobile applications allow using digital nudging methods to motivate citizens to adopt sustainable mobility behaviours. The behaviour change intervention of digital nudging is a relatively low-cost method while avoiding political issues associated with unpopular “hard” measures. However, use of digital nudging to shift mobility mode choice towards “green” options requires sufficient sustainable mobility infrastructure and services to be appropriate.

The DyMoN approach of situation-aware nudging

Digital nudging has been proposed for promoting sustainable behaviours in different fields, including urban mobility. Various behaviour change techniques have already been applied, e.g., informational campaigns, social norms, mobility challenges and other game-like methods, among others. The DyMoN project developed and trialled an innovative approach that allows using such methods in combination with situation-awareness. The approach takes account of the fact that the situation in which a nudge reaches a person can be crucial for a successful behavioural intervention. Regarding the promotion of sustainable mobility choices situational factors, for example, include weather, traffic situation, proximity to public transport stations or cycling routes.

DyMoN created a “Nudging Repository”, a set of 166 different nudges that are characterized by mobility mode (walk, cycle, public transport), trip purpose (leisure, commuting), behaviour change technique, situational factors, nudge text, timing, and general use (when a nudge can also be used not linked to specific situational data). The behaviour change techniques include action planning (e.g., a sustainable mobility trip), information about consequences (e.g.,

positive health or environmental effects), social comparison (e.g., information on what others do), prompts/cues (e.g., reminders to keep using sustainable mobility modes), among others.

To enable situation awareness, DyMoN has brought together in a data hub various data on situational factors as mentioned above (D3.1). The data hub allows connecting the current GPS location information of users of a smartphone app with such data that define their immediate situation. Based on the identified situation and user preferences regarding sustainable mobility modes the DyMoN system can select appropriate nudges from the Nudging Repository and send these situation-aware notifications to the users of the smartphone app.

A tendency in digital nudging has been trying to collect ever more data about the users and their mobility behaviour via their smartphones to possibly improve the nudging through user tracking and profiling. Instead, the DyMoN approach uses situational factors external to the user to support sustainable mobility choices while minimizing the demand for personal data. The key data the DyMoN system needs for providing nudges is a user's sustainable mobility preferences and location when connecting with the system. But this data is deleted after sending the nudge notifications, i.e., there is no tracking or profiling of the user's mobility behaviour.

The DyMoN approach has been successfully applied in a pilot demonstration with commuters in the city of Salzburg as well as expanded to other scenarios and use cases in a hackathon in Uppsala.

As a research pathway project, the focus of the DyMoN project has been on applied R&D aimed to explore, evaluate and disseminate new ways of promoting urban sustainable mobility behaviour, particularly through digital nudging towards relevant choices. The project results have generated measurable impacts regarding user communities in the countries of the consortium members, other European countries and beyond.

The impact deliverable starts with a description of impact areas that DyMoN set out to achieve, dividing impacts into scientific impact, societal and environmental impact and economic impact. This is further divided into sections on impact within the project duration and impact beyond the project duration.

2 Scientific impact

The DyMoN consortium has achieved considerable scientific impact through its interdisciplinary approach (involving psychology, social sciences, innovation, geography, geoinformatics, software development) by disseminating results, publishing articles, involving relevant stakeholders during the project as well as and expanding knowledge in following research projects.

2.1 During the project

The consortium within the DyMoN project set out to achieve the scientific impact by disseminating results and products of the project to the interdisciplinary applied R&D community. For this community, active at the intersection of smart sustainable cities, urban mobility and behaviour change, especially the DyMoN results and insights are important. This includes the review of nudging methods (D2.1a), the user requirements for digital tools stemming from the user needs (D2.1b), the structure and workings of the data hub (D3.1), simulation model of nudging (D3.2), the nudging repository (D2.2a) and the handbook on digital nudging for sustainable mobility (Luger-Bazinger et al., 2023). During the project time, we were able to reach up to 2700 (direct reach) and 9600 (indirect) representatives of the R&D and scientific community with specific events and workshops (details can be found in the results on dissemination, D6.3).

Furthermore, over the three years of the project, representatives participated as speakers in 14 conferences, and four scientific publications were released in various international journals, as listed below:

- [“Ethics of digital, data-based nudges: The need for responsible innovation”](#) (authors: Claudia Luger-Bazinger, Rodessa May Marquez, Carlotta Harms, Martin Loidl, Dana Kaziyeva, Veronika Hornung-Prähauser; source: “ISPIM Innovation Conference Proceedings”).
- [“Digital interventions for sustainable mobility behaviour: Gender bias in innovation”](#) (authors: Claudia Luger-Bazinger, Rodessa May Marquez, Veronika Hornung-Prähauser; source: “ISPIM Innovation Conference Proceedings”).
- [“Digital behavioural interventions for sustainable mobility: A review of behaviour change techniques in mobile apps”](#) (authors: Claudia Luger-Bazinger, Guntram Geser, Veronika Hornung-Prähauser; source: “The Behavioural Economics Guide”).
- [“Unlocking the potential of digital, situation-aware nudging for promoting sustainable mobility”](#) (authors: Martin Loidl, Dana Kaziyeva, Robin Wendel, Claudia Luger-

Bazinger, Matthias Seeber, Charalampos Stamatopoulos; source: "Sustainability", Volume 15, Issue 14, July 2023).

Moreover, 150 copies of the Handbook were printed and distributed to the target audience, primarily in Austria. Additionally, as of 22 February 2024, 143 people have downloaded it.

DyMoN Summer School

The University of Salzburg, together with Salzburg Research and TraffiCon, organized and hosted a summer school on "GIS and psychology meet for behavioural change in mobility: Innovative digital interventions for sustainable mobility" in the context of the DyMoN project. From June 27th to July 6th, 2023, 12 participants from around the globe with a very diverse domain background gathered in Salzburg. Participants were selected from a total of 369 interested people. The objective of the event was to reflect on internal and external motivators and deterrents for sustainable mobility in an inter- and transdisciplinary research setting. The summer school consisted of lectures, hands-on workshops, group work with exchange opportunities with citizens and stakeholders from public administration, as well as a large scientific conference with a total workload of 3 ECTS. In the hands-on workshops, concepts from the lectures were transferred into practice, equipping the participants with a rich skill set. The group work built on this, with a set of real-world challenges from which groups of students could choose. Under the supervision of experts from the DyMoN project team, four groups worked independently on the respective topics ("Safety and Accessibility at Salzburg Main Station", "Bike Lanes and Safety: Bikeability in the Field", "Features of a future Mobility Hub at Aighhof Station", "Beyond Visuals: Harnessing the Power of Mobility Dashboards"). The results of the group work were presented in a poster session at the GI_Salzburg conference. Impressions from the summer school are collected in a short movie: <https://vimeo.com/867896898>.

Figure 1: The DyMoN Summer School on sustainable mobility

2.2 Beyond the project

Beyond the project, the consortium was able to acquire the following new research projects and scientific collaborations.

Simulation Model

The simulation model serves as foundation for more advanced and specialized models of sustainable mobility that more closely connects the cost function the actual cost of citizens. This has the potential to be used in municipal calculations for estimating the price of nudges, or if in fact the nudges would push citizens into a more personal economic favourable position, as the simulation model has indicated (see a more detailed description in the section on societal and environmental impact).

DyMoN Summer School

The summer school turned out to be fruitful beyond conveying skills and disseminating project results from DyMoN, as it enlarged the professional and academic network. This resulted, for instance, in a joint research project with the home institution of one of the summer school participants (DUT project CITWIN, University of Liège) and an invitation to a university's

podcast series of another home institution of a participant (Tartu Geo Podcast, upcoming episode with M. Loidl).

New research project: SuCoLo

The project SuCoLo (Fostering sustainable consumer behaviour with inclusive bicycle logistics infrastructure in urban outskirts - SuCoLo), lead by Salzburg Research (with Sustainability InnoCenter being a partner in the consortium), aims to provide a solid conceptual, methodological and empirical understanding of how to motivate sustainable consumer behaviour and deploy inclusive bicycle logistics to foster net-zero ways of delivery and pick-up of goods in urban outskirts. Digital behaviour change methods will be developed to encourage citizens to use sustainable logistics choices, building on psychological models of behaviour change already explored in DyMoN. SuCoLo will further investigate the required infrastructure and other needs of citizens, logistics providers and e-shops within a smart urban bicycle logistics ecosystem, using community-centred and data-driven planning approaches with simulation models. Pick-up stations for ordered goods will be designed to serve also as social places for residents, with a focus on accessibility and inclusiveness. The concepts will be collaboratively design and tested in Salzburg, Leipzig and Merano. The behaviour change strategies will build on the results and insights of DyMoN (especially the nudging repository and the handbook).

New research project: PISTIS

The HORIZON project PISTIS, led by the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft, is dedicated to fostering a federated data sharing/trading and monetisation platform that ensures secure, trusted, and controlled exchange and usage of proprietary data assets and data-driven insights. PISTIS aims to enhance existing technologies and methodologies, including federated data discovery and sharing, Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs), data non-fungible tokens (NFTs), AI-driven data quality assessment, and monetisation strategies. These advancements are designed to build trust among participants and alleviate their concerns. Stakeholders will establish a distributed network combining both existing and new data spaces, incorporating governance models introduced by PISTIS to break down data silos. This approach aims to recognize the inherent value of data and increase it through the creation of derivative assets in a manner that is both fair and transparent.

Within this project, TraffiCon's role involves leveraging the newly established data space to develop two key components. Firstly, a methodology will be crafted to convert extended

Floating Car Data into various emission metrics. Secondly, the project will see the creation of a corporate mobility management dashboard. This dashboard will integrate real-time data on weather conditions and emission levels across selected locations, promoting eco-friendly and healthy commuting options. By offering sustainable mobility alternatives, such as bicycles or public transport, and employing textual prompts known as "nudges," the dashboard aims to encourage users to make environmentally responsible mobility choices. The DyMoN dashboard was the groundwork for this project.

3 Societal and Environmental Impact

At the base of the DyMoN project is the goal to support individual behaviour change. When it comes to mobility, this topic is often discussed from a systemic and aggregated perspective, for example, in the modal share, which expresses the percentage of people using a particular form of mobility mode. For DyMoN, the consortium took the respective individual, who shows a specific behaviour, into the focus of the project, to develop methods to support a behaviour change towards more sustainable mobility choices. With the knowledge and results that have been produced by DyMoN, it is expected that mobility labs, cities and municipalities, politicians as well as interest group can be supported in their efforts to motivate more sustainable mobility behaviour and achieve societal change, which then leads to a positive environmental impact within cities and urban areas. Therefore, we discuss these two aspects together in this section, with a focus on environmental impact beyond the project duration.

3.1 During the project

The consortium within the DyMoN project set out to achieve societal as well as environmental impact during the project phase, especially by disseminating results to target groups that are actively trying to bring new campaigns, strategies and policies for more sustainable mobility behaviour into practice:

- *Urban mobility labs* explore new mobility concepts and solutions involving local groups of researchers, developers, city managers and citizens. They are interested in the more practical side of digital sustainable mobility nudging, e.g. proof of concept, useful tools, and engagement of mobility managers and citizens, and more concerned with putting into practice results and products from DyMoN and work with publications such as the DyMoN Handbook. These labs were specifically invited to the DyMoN webinar series (see below).
- *Smart city networks*: Existing knowledge networks of smart cities, among other topics, are interested in sustainable mobility management, including how to achieve necessary behaviour changes of citizens. In addition to CIVITAS (with active living labs), such networks include the POLIS group of European cities and regions (network of 70+ administrative bodies), and the Open Agile Smart Cities network (150+ members in 30 countries), that is directly involved in DyMoN.
- *Mobility policy and planning*: Cities aim to provide choices of sustainable mobility modes (e.g. Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans - SUMP), but also need to promote their adoption. While city policies and plans consider the need of behaviour changes, the use of digital nudging for adoption has become a topic only in recent years. In addition

to the R&D focused work, DyMoN aimed to support this topic by providing knowledge and recommendations on the appropriate use of digital nudging, through European and national platforms (e.g. ELTIS - Urban Mobility Observatory, EPOMM - European Platform on Mobility Management, and individual city websites). ELTIS shared the announcement of the DyMoN webinar series and the consortium had a special interest in disseminating relevant results to these platforms.

- *Supporting smart city managers and city representatives:* The DyMoN framework is built to support smart city managers in visualizing, evaluating and realizing sustainable mobility goals. With DyMoN webinars, city representatives received the tools and resources to successfully implement the DyMoN framework in their cities. This group was especially reached through workshops and the webinar series.

The analysis of the dissemination results showed the following (see D6.3 for more detailed information): In total, 150 copies of the Handbook were printed and distributed to the target audience, primarily in Austria. Additionally, as of 22 February 2024, 143 people have downloaded it. Partners presented the project at 14 conferences.

In total, 36 participants representing cities from different European countries took part in think tanks in November 2021 - February 2022. Each event was published on the Eventbrite platform's website and promoted on LinkedIn, generating 700-900 impressions each time. Also, eleven in-depth individual interviews were conducted with a diverse group of smart city stakeholders, involving city representatives, urban and transport planners and mobility managers from Sweden, Spain, Germany and Luxembourg.

The webinars were attended by 124 participants, with some individuals participating in two or more workshops. Additionally, all four webinars have 136 views on YouTube (February 2024).

DyMoN Summer School

The transdisciplinary design of the DyMoN summer school resulted in touchpoints with policy makers from the Salzburg region. Local stakeholders from the urban mobility lab at the regional public transport operator as well as from the public administration of the city of Salzburg provided challenges that were presented to the participants. Results from topics that were chosen by the summer school participants were then presented to these stakeholders in an interactive poster session at the GI_Salzburg conference. Besides, the organizers of the summer school hosted a panel discussion with national and regional experts at the same conference.

Figure 2: Reception for participants of the DyMoN Summer School from the City of Salzburg at Schloss Mirabell (Foto: wildbild).

DyMoN Hackathon

In Uppsala, Sweden, the proof of concept within DyMoN was conducted as an international hackathon (see D5.1 for details). The Hackathon was organised with the aim of finding solutions for sustainable development and promoting sustainable, safe and clean mobility, using nudging as a tool for effecting changes, communicating and scaling the DyMoN concept. The “hackers” had to find ways of distributing nudges for different cities and use cases.

The “Sustainable mobility Hackathon & Meet UP” (SUMMUP) was held on 11-12 May 2023 in a hybrid format: both physically at Green Innovation Park in Uppsala and virtually on Zoom, YouTube and other online streaming channels. Additionally, participants had the opportunity to watch the event in real time and ask questions on YouTube or via the online community on Slack.

The coordination of this event was directed by Sustainability InnoCenter (Uppsala, Sweden). In addition to the DyMoN project’s consortium, local partners from Swedish cities, including key actors in their innovation systems, joined the initiative (see Figure 3). These partners were Uppsala University, Uppsala Innovation Centre, the county of Uppsala, Uppsala municipality, Green Innovation Park, Gävle municipality, Gävle Innovation Hub, DrivHuset, Världklass Uppsala, Ericsson, Nudgd (digital service provider), and many others. As can be seen by the

diverse members that participated in the hackathon, both cities, municipalities as well as private companies interested in sustainable mobility were involved.

Attendance at the event was open to individuals, but engagement in the hackathon necessitated the formation or joining of a team, with solo entries not allowed. Organizers actively facilitated the team formation process, leading to the creation of 11 teams. Overall, 128 individuals enthusiastically took part in the hackathon. The event saw participation from a total of 200 individuals, comprising jury members, partners, and enthusiasts interested in the mobility theme. Moreover, the Hackathon's website drew approximately 7,000 unique visitors.

Figure 3: Partners of the “Sustainable mobility Hackathon & Meet UP”.

The participating “hackers” formed teams and had to select and solve one of three challenges that had been developed in close cooperation with the Uppsala Municipality, the Uppsala University, and the Gävle Municipality, respectively (see Figure 4). Two of the three challenges were stated by a city or municipality, underlining the societal impact of the DyMoN project and how closely involved these stakeholders were within the project.

Figure 4: The posters with the titles of the hackathon challenges.

DyMoN Webinar Series

The DyMoN webinar series included four sessions focusing on different aspects of the project. The sessions provided an in-depth insight into the topics included in the DyMoN handbook, and were targeted at cities, municipalities, as well as other researchers looking to work with the DyMoN results. The webinars were attended by 124 participants, with some individuals participating in two or more workshops. Additionally, all four webinars have 136 views on YouTube (February 2024).

Session 1: An interdisciplinary view on sustainable urban mobility behaviour

The first session was held on November 16th 2023 and introduced the project and highlighted the importance of sustainable mobility within cities. The speakers brought together a psychological view (Dr. Claudia Luger-Bazinger) with a view from geo-informatics (Dr. Martin Loidl) to show the advantages of an interdisciplinary view on sustainable mobility. These experts provided unique insights into sustainable mobility from their respective fields. The session covered the COM-B model of behaviour, a concept by Michie, van Stralen, & West (2011), and its application to mobility behaviour, along with strategies for developing effective behavioural interventions. Additionally, the geographical aspect of the webinar explored the origins and various elements of sustainable mobility, emphasizing considerations for enhancing conditions that favour sustainable mobility modes. The recording of the session can be found on YouTube under [this link](#).

Figure 5: A Screenshot of the recording of the first webinar session on an interdisciplinary view on sustainable urban mobility behaviour

Session 2: Digitally-enabled behaviour change for sustainable mobility

The second session of the DyMoN webinar series, held on December 7th, focused on the use of digital tools for promoting sustainable mobility. It emphasized the choice between "hard measures" like policies and infrastructure, and "soft measures" such as behavioural interventions and nudges. The session featured discussions with Dr. Claudia Luger-Bazinger and David Leistner on digital behaviour change, nudging, and situation-aware nudges.

Participants were introduced to the theoretical background of the DyMoN project, the COM-B model, and the practical aspects of its handbook. The seminar highlighted the importance of understanding human behaviour and the role of digital tools in shaping mobility behaviour. The use of smartphone apps and other digital tools as examples of nudges that can lead to behaviour change in mobility was a key point of discussion.

A practical case study was examined through the field test in Salzburg's Science City Aktiv Mobil. Participants learned about designing digital behaviour interventions, using a canvas from the handbook as a guide. This session provided insights into the intersection of digital technology and sustainable mobility, demonstrating how digital nudges can complement traditional policy measures. Again, the session was recorded and is [publicly available on YouTube](#).

Session 3: Using data to support sustainable mobility behaviour

The third session of the DyMoN webinar series, held on January 11th, 2024, explored the intersection of digital behavioural interventions and context-specific insights in sustainable mobility. Experts Dr. Martin Loidl and Sebastian Gatscha from TraffiCon led the session.

This webinar emphasized the critical role of situational variables in mobility decisions, illustrating how integrating these elements into a Geographical Information System (GIS) leads to effective "situation-aware nudges". The session highlighted the increased effectiveness of interventions tailored to the real-time context of individuals.

Participants were introduced to the innovative use of collected data, particularly its integration into a data dashboard that visually presents key sustainable mobility indicators. The webinar also shed light on the modular IT infrastructure that enables the delivery of these situation-aware nudges.

Overall, the session showcased the transformative potential of situational awareness in mobility behaviour, underscoring the practical implications of GIS integration and data application in crafting sustainable mobility solutions. The recording can be found on YouTube [under this link](#).

Session 4: Learnings and recommendations for sustainable mobility from the Dynamic Nudge project

The fourth session of the DyMoN webinar series, conducted on February 1st, 2024, provided a comprehensive reflection on the project's journey and its impact on sustainable urban mobility. The webinar focused on key learnings and policy recommendations derived from the project's initiatives.

The session commenced with David Leistner discussing the Salzburg field test, which demonstrated the technical feasibility of the DyMoN framework and offered preliminary insights into the behavioural effectiveness of situational mobility nudges. Harris Stamatopoulos then presented the DyMoN hackathon in Uppsala, Sweden, highlighting the framework's flexibility in addressing varied mobility challenges.

Dr. Claudia Luger-Bazinger, the project manager, synthesized the project's outcomes into ten crucial learnings and recommendations. These recommendations emphasized viewing digital behaviour change tools as supplements to traditional "hard interventions," the importance of utilizing existing apps and online communities, and the need for early involvement of citizens, representatives, and stakeholders in campaign design.

The session underscored the project's significant contributions to understanding and enhancing sustainable urban mobility. It provided valuable insights into engaging the public, involving key stakeholders, and the factors crucial for the success of digital campaigns aimed at promoting sustainable mobility. Under [this link](#) the recording of the fourth session can be found.

The backbone of the webinar series was the DyMoN Handbook presented in the following part of this deliverable.

DyMoN Handbook

The [DyMoN Handbook “Digital Nudging for sustainable mobility”](#) is one of the key results of the project. It is targeted at anyone interested in motivating people to use more sustainable mobility options, like switching over from driving their car to bicycling, walking or taking public transport. With the handbook, the DyMoN consortium wants to offer an easy to understand, yet in-depth perspective on changing behaviour: Readers can learn to think about changing mobility behaviour in a more holistic way by identifying barriers and facilitators of individual behaviour through a model of behaviour change. Readers will also realize how digital tools can be used to change behaviour, and that data can help these tools be more effective by incorporating current situations and context. The DyMoN handbook explains digitally enabled behaviour change for sustainable mobility, which means using digital tools to change behaviour in one’s physical environment. The handbook explains in a clear manner the basics of behaviour change, how digital tools can help, gives hands-on instructions and provides canvases for designing behavioural interventions for sustainable mobility.

Figure 6: Cover of the DyMoN handbook on “Digital nudging for sustainable mobility”.

The handbook has been printed and distributed also digitally. So far, the handbook has been downloaded 143 times (111 from the website, 32 directly via QR code at events). The Webpage with the Download link has seen 286 unique visits until the date of export (20.02.2024). Beyond the project, a workshop on how using the handbook for motivating bicycling in municipalities is already scheduled (Radvernetzungstreffen Salzburg, May 2024), plus more workshops and presentations are planned.

The DyMoN handbook as well as the DyMoN dashboard are also planned to be presented at the “Long Night of Research” (May 2024) in Salzburg, where universities and research institutes present their work to the general public and other interested researchers.

Figure 7: The DyMoN Dashboard that accompanied the field test in Salzburg and can be found under <https://dymon.trafficcon.eu/>

3.2 Beyond the project

Simulation model

One part of the project was the development and evaluation of models for travels that included nudging. As part of the impact assessment one important aspect here was to assess the large scale impact of the simulation models, presented in Deliverable 3.2, for a city of a given size and over time. Full details regarding the simulation model can be found in Deliverable 3.2.

The nudging model development and results are briefly summarized here as a basis for impact assessment. A motivation for the work is that simulations of mobility by different modes are important to be able to understand the impact of nudges influencing mobility choices. The mobility nudging model was based on published results in (Wallentin & Loidl, 2015; Kaziyeva, Loidl, & Wallentin, 2021), where the model was built in the GAMA platform (Axhausen, Horni, & Nagel, 2016), and the model developed for this delivery was developed in MATSim. The model is fully spatiotemporal and is based on city road networks. As an illustration, a snapshot from the simulation model of the traffic intensity on the road network simulations of Salzburg, Austria, is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: A thermal map of traffic road network usage in a snapshot from the simulation model.

In terms of results, based on the simulation model for X percent changing from car to bike as mode of mobility, the utility function cost for the plans to take car (original plans) and costs for other travels are presented along with travel duration in Table 1. This simulation was made for the entire Salzburg, Austria.

Table 1: Average score € per person and mean traveling duration (hr:minute/person/day).

<i>Nudged percentage</i>	<i>Score (€)</i>	<i>Travelling duration</i>
<i>Original plans</i>	48.8	02:59
25%	52.3	02:57
33%	52.5	02:58
50%	52.6	03:01
67%	52.0	03:04
75%	51.7	03:05
100%	50.6	03:10

Based on the results, shifting to bike is generally more beneficial than using a car, for at least the city size of Salzburg, and at least to 50% of the population. This means that there is a reduced spending on mobility in this shift. This means that if inhabitants are habitual and taking the car, but rational economically, nudging for sustainable mobility modes could potentially lead to new behaviours stable over time. The exact numbers on the economic impact is difficult, given that the scoring has to be normalized with respect to an actual test case for this. The nudging framework is yet to be implemented on city scale beyond the proof of concept, so there are no significant short-term economic or environmental impacts.

Scientifically, in the long term, if assuming nudging on large scale for sustainable mobility has been carried out to a large extent, then it is possible to have higher predictive accuracy for the effect of nudging, which in turn could lead to the development of more advanced nudging techniques, and also lead to higher precision in implementing the nudging for cities. While some mobility nudges seem economically rational, such as the change from taking the car to bike in the simulation model, there will be nudges that require economical incentives or target social norms. With a more mature mobility nudging field, which this project contributes to, the cost for gaining a particular impact in a city can be more precisely determined.

The societal of impact of large scale transitions from car usage to bike usage for mobility would, by the results of the simulation model, be economically advantageous for the inhabitants while simultaneously reduce emissions. That is, the model results suggests that the costs from municipal or governmental perspective for essentially permanent behavioural change would be that of initiating a limited session of nudging for sustainable mobility.

Effect on behaviour in the long-term

Meta-analysis on the effect of so called soft measures on reduction of car use (such as motivational campaigns, incentives, as well as nudges) suggest that they have a small effect (Semenescu, Gavreliuc & Sârbescu, 2020). However, since nudges and other behavioural interventions are cheaper and often easier to implement than hard measures such as law, regulations and new infrastructure, these soft measures are well suited to be used in support of already existing efforts. Most cities, municipalities and even neighbourhoods have already implemented soft measures in their efforts to reduce individual car use, for example, mobility campaigns or incentives. In addition, many mobile apps are also using digital methods for changing mobility behaviour (Luger-Bazinger, Geser, Hornung-Prähauser, 2023). These efforts would be boosted by using the results of the DyMoN project to further structure and professionalize motivational campaigns and nudges. Adding to this the situation-aware aspect of the project that also considers the current context of a person, it is expected that this can have an even greater effect, as results from other fields, for example health (Wang & Miller, 2019), have showed. The necessary results, insights and tools have been designed and tested within the DyMoN project (see D2.2a for the nudging repository, D3.1 for the data hub, the DyMoN Handbook as well as D4.1 for the description of the proof of concept phase) and can be used in order to shift mobility behaviour from individual car use to walking, bicycling or public transport. If cities can be supported in such a way, this would mean a better quality of life in urban areas, with better air quality, less noise and more room for people instead of cars.

4 Economic Impact

With DyMoN being a research project, economic impact was not a direct target of the consortium. However, several products and results of DyMoN have received interest of companies and could be developed after the project.

DyMoN Handbook and nudging repository

The DyMoN handbook as well as the nudging repository received interest not only from researchers, city representatives and municipalities, but also from companies, looking to professionalize their mobility services when it comes to behaviour, joining the webinars as well as already incorporating insights from the handbook in their work. For example, the consortium held meetings with [Nudgd](#), a company specialized in behavioural design and nudging, offering a web-based application for mobility nudging, in order to find ways for future cooperations.

DyMoN Dashboard

In the context of evolving tools and services for mobility analysis, two products stand out as having the potential for increased use in the future. First, there's the newly revamped DTM (Dynamic Traffic Monitor) from Trafficon, their standard tool for mobility analyses. This tool is undergoing significant redevelopment, with many research projects and ideas being integrated into it, especially the integration and analysis of public transport and bicycle data. This indicates a broader application and utility in understanding and optimizing cycling traffic and infrastructure. Second, the demand for Urban Data Dashboards is on the rise. These dashboards cater to two types of users: those involved in traffic and urban planning and those designed for citizens. By providing real-time data and insights, these dashboards can significantly aid in making informed decisions for urban development and personal mobility. The DyMoN dashboard enabled a first step into this demand, and could be further developed by project partner Trafficon. Furthermore, the motivation for behavioural change continues to be a focus, pursued through the concept of nudging. While Trafficon is currently in the process of acquisition and tendering, the exact outcomes and implementations are yet to be defined. However, the potential for these tools to influence mobility patterns and encourage more sustainable mobility choices is an exciting prospect for the future.

Hackathon

In addition to the core partners of the DyMoN project, various local Swedish partners actively supported the international Hackathon in Uppsala. Key players in their innovation systems, such as Uppsala Innovation Centre, the Green Innovation Park, Gävle Innovation Hub, Node Gotland, DrivHuset and others played a significant role. On the private business side, the initiative brought together the following companies:

- **Ericsson**, a Swedish multinational networking and telecommunications company;
- **Nudgd**, a digital service provider that provided one of the hackathon challenges;
- **Energimyndigheten**, a Swedish state administrative authority for questions about the use and supply of energy;
- **Sensative**, a tech company offering IoT services and products for a wide range of applications;
- **Nuxon**, a software development company;
- **UL**, an integrated transport authority responsible for public transport buses and trains in Uppsala County, Sweden;
- **ChromaWay**, a blockchain company, and others.

5 Conclusion

Cities in Europe are facing the challenge on how to reduce individual car use and shift mobility towards more sustainable forms such as walking, bicycling or public transport. This is not only question of a reduction of GHG-emissions, but also a question of quality of life within cities—if there are less cars in the urban areas, this means better air quality, less noise, and more space for people instead of cars. To achieve this, cities can either rely on hard measures such as laws, regulations, bans or new infrastructure. Such hard measures are not always possible, can be very expensive and are not always effective by themselves. Therefore, soft measures are needed in order to support these efforts, targeting social norms, motivation and psychological factors. Behavioural interventions, one subgroup of them being nudges, are one method to support changing mobility behaviour and can be a potential cornerstone for a mobility transition. DyMoN as interdisciplinary project has brought together psychology, social sciences, innovation management, geoinformatics, software development and mathematics for expanding knowledge and results on changing mobility behaviour by using soft measures in the form of behavioural interventions.

Within this research project, the consortium has achieved not only scientific, but also societal, environmental and economic impact that goes beyond the project duration. This project has delivered work on development, implementation and simulation of digital, data-driven nudges in real life settings. It has broadened the scientific field by providing new approaches to mobility behaviour change and the design of nudges and behavioural interventions in the mobility field, and has disseminated the results to cities, municipalities and local communities, supporting the modal shift towards more sustainable mobility in its environmental impact. It also opened the door to economic studies of nudging that could be tested in real life settings. In the long run, the project has impact on the design and evaluation of sustainable mobility nudges so that there can be potential wide-spread use of this in cities that is followed by a better quality of life within urban areas.

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